

Tsallis Entropy, Function-Inverse Function Pair and Kaniadakis Stationary Distribution

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In a series of notes, we argued that the inverse function Q of a distribution function $f(1/T(e-u))$ seems to play a role in a generalized entropy density defined by $-f Q(f)$ ((1)). We argued this holds for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) and Kaniadakis cases and that function-inverse functions played a role in the Tsallis situation. In this note, we wish to show that using Tsallis entropy and the idea of an inverse function one may obtain directly the q -exponential Tsallis distribution. We further argue that the idea of a generalized entropy density ((1)) may play other roles. In a previous note, we argued that fugacity plays the role of a normalization constant for the MB case and that MB free energy was then proportional to u , the chemical potential. This follows because MB entropy (Shannon's entropy) makes use of a function-inverse function pair namely \ln and $f=\exp(-x/T)$ where $x=e-u$. Thus, ((1)) leads to TS consisting of three terms $Eave$ and $-u - \ln(V)/T$. We argued this may also be the case for Kaniadakis k -entropy because $Q= 1/2k (f^k-f^{-k})$ is the inverse of the Kaniadakis distribution $f(x)= [\sqrt{1+k^2x^2}+kx]^{1/k}$ where $x=1/T(e-u)$

Kaniadakis (1) has recently (2018) developed a generalized statistical theory based on non-linear kinematics. In this theory, he defines a constrained entropy $S1= S + E-uN$. Thus, it seems the idea of a generalized entropy ((1)) leading to $E-uN$ may be important in this theory.

Tsallis Entropy, Distribution Function and Function-Inverse Function Pair

The Tsallis entropy is given by (2):

$$S_q = k/(q-1) [1 - \sum_i p_i^q] \quad \text{where } p_i \text{ is the probability and } \sum_i p_i = 1 \quad ((2))$$

We set $k=1$. For the continuous case \sum_i becomes $\int dx$. In the $q=1$ limit, S_q becomes the MB entropy $-\sum_i p(x) \ln(p(x))$. This seems to follow from (2) where:

$$\lim_{b \rightarrow 1} d/db \sum_i p_i^b = \lim_{b \rightarrow 1} d/db \sum_i \exp[\ln(p_i) b] = \sum_i \ln(p_i) p_i$$

For the Tsallis case, the q derivative (3) is used:

$$d/db |_q f(x) = [f(qx) - f(x)] / (qx-x) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Then,}$$

$$\lim_{b \rightarrow 1} d/db |_q = [\sum_i p_i^{qb} - \sum_i p_i^b] / [qb-b] = 1/(q-1) [\sum_i p_i^q - 1]$$

From (2), it follows that $d/db |_q$ for $q=1$ equals d/db .

A possible Tsallis distribution, called the q -exponential is given in (4) as:

$$(2-q) [1+(1-q)x]^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((3))$$

The factor (2-q) comes from normalizing ((3)) with integration bounds at 0 and infinite. If $x = -1/T(e-u)$ it is not clear if 0 is the lower integration bound. For the $q=1$ limit, the normalization factor becomes 1 and:

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} [1+(1-q)x]^{1/(1-q)} = \exp(x) \quad ((4))$$

It has been argued that ((4)) is already normalized by the fugacity. Thus, one obtains the normalized MB case.

A point we wish to make in this note, is that one may obtain ((4)) from S_q ((2)) by using the idea of function - inverse function pairs. Starting with ((2)), one may try to reverse the process in the following way:

1. Start with x .
2. Multiply by $(q-1)$ the inverse of $1/(q-1)$ in ((2)).
3. Subtract 1 and multiply by -1 to obtain $(1-q)x+1$

Now, we argue a generalized entropy should be in the form: $-\sum p_i Q(p_i) = \sum p_i Q(1/p_i)$ so one needs to factor out a p_i so p_i^q is p_i time p_i^{q-1} . Thus, one obtains $p_i = [(1-q)x+1]^{1/(1-q)}$ which matches ((3)) without the (2-q) normalization.

There is also the case of the Tsallis q Gaussian: $C [(1-q)x^2+1]^{1/(1-q)}$

It seems that in this case, one is setting $x^2 = .5m p^2$

Thus, function-inverse function pairs seem to play a role in the MB, Kaniadakis and Tsallis q exponential cases. This means that in all three cases:

$$-T \sum_i p_i \ln(p_i) = \text{Ave}(E) - u \quad \text{where } u \text{ is the chemical potential. } ((4))$$

Thus, ((4)) should appear in a generalized theory which includes MB, Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions. It should be noted that it has been argued in the literature that nonlinear Brownian motion theories, using the Planck-Fokker equation may yield a Tsallis distribution. (5)

Kaniadakis Generalized Statistical Model Based on NonLinear Kinematics

In (1), Kaniadakis develops a statistical model based on nonlinear kinematics. He argues that two particle collisions depend on $g(f_1, f_2) g(f_3, f_4)$ where $f_1 + f_2 \rightarrow f_3 + f_4$. Here g is an unknown function and f_i the distribution function. He argues that:

$g(f_1, f_2) = k(f_1)$ where k is an unknown function. For the linear case, k becomes the identity so $k(f_1) = f_1$.

Kaniadakis defines:

$\ln[k(fs)] = 1/T (KE + V - u)$ where KE =kinetic energy, V potential and u, the chemical potential

For the linear case (i.e the MB case) $k(fs)=fs$ so one immediately obtains the MB stationary distribution.

Kaniadiakis defines a constrained entropy as:

$$K = - \text{Integral over phase space} \int df \ln(k(f)) - 1/T (E-uN) \quad ((5))$$

The first term on the RHS of ((5)) is a time-dependent entropy and the second seems to be linked to a generalized entropy related to the stationary distribution i.e.

$$- \int \text{Integral phase space} f(x) Q(f(x)) \quad \text{where } Q \text{ and } f \text{ are inverses and } x=1/T(E-uN).$$

For the MB, Kaniadakis and Tsallis cases, it seems Q is directly related to the respective theories. For the MB case, $Q=\ln$, for the Kaniadakis case one has $Q(f(x))= x = 1/2k (f^k - f^{-k})$ and for the Tsallis case, we have argued above that one may take S_q and find an inverse function using a certain recipe that involves factoring out an f (because one has $fQ(f)$) to obtain $f(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain the q-exponential directly from the Tsallis entropy S_q using the idea of function-inverse function. We argue that a generalized entropy for the MB, Kaniadakis and Tsallis cases may be represented by:

$$- \sum \text{over } i f(x_i) Q(f(x_i)) \quad \text{where } Q \text{ and } f \text{ are inverses.}$$

If $x=1/T(e-uN)$ this implies that the generalized entropy is $-\sum \text{over } i f(x_i) 1/T (e-uN) = -1/T (E-uN)$ a term which appears as part of the constrained entropy in Kaniadakis statistical theory (1) based on nonlinear dynamics.

References

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